

Mememes in Higher Education: Creation, Sharing & Considerations

A growing body of research demonstrates the value of mememes in learning and teaching — from promoting reflection and wellbeing to enabling creative assessment. This guide supports educators and students in using mememes effectively and responsibly.

WHAT THE RESEARCH TELLS US — MEMES SUPPORT...

Expressing reflection on class or course content

Tidy et al, 2024a; Tammi & Rautio, 2023

Supporting module evaluation

Taylor & Stump, 2023

Exploring wellbeing

Ask & Abidin, 2018; Maples, 2023

Development of skills

Kayali & Altuntas, 2021; Peel & Bran, 2023

Engaging learners by enriching and enhancing the learning experience

Kyrpa, 2022; Antón-Sancho et al, 2022; Boyle, 2022; Anam Shahbaz et al, 2024

Allowing for the expression of student emotion

Mullen et al, 2026

Enhance formative assessment

Brown, 2020

Research method

Tidy et al, 2024b

CREATING MEMES — APPROACHES FOR EDUCATORS AND STUDENTS

Online meme generators

Easy and convenient. Choose from template images or GIFs and add your own text, then share directly.

e.g. Imgflip Meme Generator, Canva Meme Maker, Imgmeme

Photo editing tools

Add words or effects to chosen images — either creator's own images or those supplied by the educator.

e.g. Photoshop, MS Paint

AI-generated mememes

Use AI tools to create both image and text elements as part of the meme-making process.

e.g. Adobe Firefly

SHARING MEMES — APPROACHES BY CONTEXT

Informal

Digital sharing platforms

Ideal for real-time sharing to facilitate reflection and group

Semi-formal

Submission to educator

Educator reflects on and curates mememes into a digital slideshow or

Formal

VLE submission

Where mememes form part of a formal formative or summative

discussion.
e.g. Padlet

printed set for teaching.

assessment, submit via the VLE.

KEY CONSIDERATIONS FOR EDUCATORS

- ◆ Memes allow participants to be creative and express themselves but this needs to be carried out within a framework that considers the wider impact of a meme
- ◆ Be clear on content expectations to avoid the creation of memes that may offend
- ◆ Be aware of "cruel memeing" — how memes can be used to express or normalise divisive views (Marlin-Bennett & Jackson, 2022)
- ◆ Be mindful of cultural differences that may mean memes have a diverse range of meanings or how participants relate to the humour within the memes
- ◆ Educators must be proficient in the process of creating memes and invested in the process for memes to be successfully deployed
- ◆ Used correctly, memes have the power to bring creativity and humour to the learning and teaching process

REFERENCES

- Anam Shahbaz, Inam, F., Abdul Wasay, Shamsa Mohsin, Zarrin Siddiqi, & Fauzia Qureshi. (2024). Study Through Memes: Using Memes as a Teaching Tool in Anatomy. *Proceedings (Shaikh Zayed Hospital)*, 38(2), 95–100. <https://doi.org/10.47489/szmc.v38i2.483>
- Antón-Sancho, Á., Nieto-Sobrino, M., Fernández-Arias, P., & Vergara-Rodríguez, D. (2022). Usability of Memes and Humorous Resources in Virtual Learning Environments. *Education Sciences*, 12(3), 208. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12030208>
- Ask, K., & Abidin, C. (2018). My life is a mess: self-deprecating relatability and collective identities in the memification of student issues. *Information, Communication & Society*, 21(6), 834–850. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2018.1437204>
- Boyle, C. (2022). How do you meme?: Using memes for information literacy instruction. *The Reference Librarian*, 63(3), 82–101. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02763877.2022.2084210>
- Brown, J. D. (2020). What Do You Meme, Professor? An Experiment Using "Memes" in Pharmacy Education. *Pharmacy*, 8(4), 202. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmacy8040202>
- Kayali, N.K. and Altuntas, A. (2021) "Using Memes in the Language Classroom," *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 9(3), p. 155.
- Kyrpa, A., Stepanenko, O., Zinchenko, V., Udovichenko, H., & Dmytruk, L. (2022). Integration of Internet Memes when teaching philological disciplines in higher education institutions. *Advanced Education*, 9(20), 45–52. <https://doi.org/10.20535/2410-8286.235947>
- Maples, G. W. (2023). High Impact, Low Mood: An Analysis of Graduate Student Attitudes and Perceptions Through PHD Memes. *International Journal of Doctoral Studies*, 18, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.28945/5075>
- Marlin-Bennett, R. and Jackson, S.T. (2022) "DIY Cruelty: The Global Political Micro-Practices of Hateful Memes," *Global Studies Quarterly*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.1093/isagsq/ksac002>
- Mullen, C., Tidy, H., Croxton, R., Williams, G., Carlyle-Davies, F., Irving-Walton, J., Nichols-Drew, L. and Page, H. (2025) 'Using memes to surface and support assessment emotion in mock courtroom assessments within the forensic sciences', *Journal of Forensic Science Education*, 8(1).
- Pele, A., & Bran, R. (2023). Testing Memes as a Teaching Tool. *Buletinul Stiintific al Universitatii Politehnica Din Timisoara. Seria Limbi Moderne*, 21, 159–165. <https://doi.org/10.59168/UDOL7818>

Tammi, T., & Rautio, P. (2023). "It was funny at first" exploring tensions in human-animal relations through internet memes with university students. *Environmental Education Research*, 29(4), 539–551. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2022.2073972>

Taylor, A. G., & Stump, P. (2023). Arts-based feedback: Using memes for midterm evaluations. *Communication Teacher*, 37(3), 182–187. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17404622.2023.2182901>

Tidy, H., Bolton-King, R. S., Croxton, R., Mullen, C., Nichols-Drew, L., Carlysle-Davies, F., Moran, K. S., & Irving-Walton, J. (2024a). Enhancing the student learning experience through memes. *Science & Justice*, 64(3), 280–288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scijus.2024.03.004>

Tidy, H., Irving-Walton, J., Currie, G., Nichols-Drew, L., & Page, H. (2024b). What do you meme?—Meme-Making as a research method. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562517.2024.2345699>